

Research Article

Paddy Piston Elevating Upland Paddy Cultivation

Grace Flavyeliz Sinong^{1,*}, Mohd Hafezan Sisa², Eva Nastasha Willie³, Evy Nathalie Yap⁴, Hazarina Ramli⁵, and Mohammad Aizatasmawi Abd Rasak⁶

¹ Faculty of Plantation and Agrotechnology, UiTM Sabah Branch, Kota Kinabalu Campus, Sabah, Malaysia; flavyeliz@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (0000-0002-7363-1861)

² Faculty of Plantation and Agrotechnology, UiTM Sabah Branch, Kota Kinabalu Campus, Sabah, Malaysia; mohdh445@uitm.edu.my

³ Faculty of Plantation and Agrotechnology, UiTM Sabah Branch, Kota Kinabalu Campus, Sabah, Malaysia

⁴ Faculty of Plantation and Agrotechnology, UiTM Sabah Branch, Kota Kinabalu Campus, Sabah, Malaysia

⁵ Faculty of Plantation and Agrotechnology, UiTM Sabah Branch, Kota Kinabalu Campus, Sabah, Malaysia

⁶ Faculty of Plantation and Agrotechnology, UiTM Sabah Branch, Kota Kinabalu Campus, Sabah, Malaysia

* Correspondence: flavyeliz@uitm.edu.my; +60197373692.

Abstract: A paddy piston is innovated to address the challenges of hilly area topography, time-consuming paddy seed sowing, and farmer's efficiency for upland paddy cultivation. To meet the precision and efficiency of paddy seed placement, the paddy piston is designed to enable farmers to carry out the planting activity more efficiently and less time-consuming. The paddy piston is equipped with a storage capacity of 800 g paddy seeds, a cone-shaped bottom for creating the planting hole, and the mechanism of grip handle, spring, and stopper to control the discharge of paddy seeds with 7-10 seeds at a time. With this tool, farmers' efficiency, precision, and productivity for the planting operation of upland paddy can be increased, leading to higher yield and sustainable production of upland paddy.

Keywords: upland paddy; seed sowing; efficient; less-time consuming; sustainable.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Rice is a staple food for millions across Southeast Asia, including the rural communities of Sabah and Sarawak, Malaysia. Among these communities, upland paddy farming is traditionally practice for home consumption and sometimes the farmers sell their surplus to earn some money. Upland paddy usually grown on terrain or hilly area under dry condition or without the presence of ponded water and irrigation system. The yield production of upland paddy in Malaysia is recorded ranging from 0.46 to 1.1 tonnes per hectare (Sohbari, Rafii, Hanafi & Latif., 2013). According to Malaysian Department of Agriculture (2021), about 51,813 ha area are planted with upland paddy in Sabah and Sarawak with yield production of 54,058 metric tonne in 2021. The yield still considered low and these are commonly due to the poor agronomy management practices and lack of nutrient management application (Hanafi, Hartinie, Shukor & Mahmud., 2009; Zainal 2015).

Upland paddy cultivation faced with numerous challenges due to the hilly area topography and the reliance on traditional farming methods known as *menugal* or *mangasok*. The conventional practices of sowing paddy seeds using traditional tools is time consuming in which it required one person to make a planting hole using the *taasok* or *tugal* and followed with another person responsible to place the paddy seeds into the planting hole made. This method often results in inconsistent seed

placement, leading to suboptimal crop yields. Moreover, the physical strain of traditional method is especially challenging for older farmers and those with limited resources. These challenges have resulted in decreased of upland paddy productivity and have discouraged younger generations from taking up this traditional agricultural practices. To address these issues, the innovation of paddy piston can provide a more efficient and less physically demanding method for cultivation of upland paddy especially on upland terrains. This innovation approach aims to provide farmers with a tool to improve seed placement accuracy and reduce labor intensity.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The paddy piston is made up with iron rod. An iron rod with 3 cm diameter that serve as the prototype body is attached with an iron rod of 6 cm diameter that has a cone shape at the bottom end. The bottom part serve as the storage for the paddy seeds in which on the side of it is equipped with a hole to insert the paddy seed inside. Then, the prototype is equipped with a grip handle, wire and spring mechanism that attached to the bottom part for the discharge of paddy seed from the opening hole of the cone shaped. The total height of the prototype is about 116cm.

Figure 1. Flowchart of project implementation.

3. FINDINGS

The paddy piston has a storage capacity up to 800 g of paddy seed. The tool is easy to operate as the user would only poke the tool into the ground and the cone shape bottom will create a planting hole for the paddy seeds. Then, by gripping the handle, a spring mechanism pulls up a stopper, allowing the release of paddy seeds from the opening hole into the planting hole. About 7-10 paddy seeds will be release at a time, and it is control by the stopper located at the side of the opening hole. The working mechanism of this tool relies on the grip handle, which control the opening hole or the stopper for the discharge of paddy seeds.

Figure 2. The (a) sketch and the (b) paddy piston prototype.

4. DISCUSSION

The innovated paddy piston facilitates the holding and seed placement simultaneously replacing the traditional methods of *Menugal* or *Mangasok* activity, thus help reducing the time and labor required for the upland paddy cultivation. The ergonomic design of the tool also reduces physical strain among farmers as the tool only require minimal effort to operate and no bending operation for the seed placement involved. Moreover, the efficiency of the tool in placing 7 - 10 paddy seeds at one time help to ensure uniform seed distribution and placement, increasing the planting efficiency and successful of seedling establishment.

The paddy piston innovation contributes to the achievements of Sustainable Development Goals. By making the sowing process more precise and efficient of seed placement, optimizing the use of resources and less labor-intensive, farmers can achieve higher yields with less physical strain. This ensures a steady supply of paddy for the local community, better income opportunities, improve livelihoods, and promote sustainable production of upland paddy. The impact of this tool spans the SGD 1, SDG 2 and SDG 12 key that emphasize on poverty reduction, food security and responsible consumption and production, respectively.

5. CONCLUSION

The paddy piston offers high efficiency and productivity of the upland paddy addressing the challenges on sowing method. This innovation product will help small scale upland paddy's farmers to enhance the productivity and yield of upland rice, improving the livelihood quality and upland paddy cultivation sector.

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